

On The Weak Fuzzy Complex Inner Products On Weak Fuzzy Complex Vector Spaces

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Abstract:

In this paper, we concentrate on the concept of inner products defined over weak fuzzy complex vector spaces and their properties. We handle the problem of orthogonality between weak fuzzy complex vector spaces defined over the ring of weak fuzzy complex numbers. Many examples will be presented to explain our work.

Keywords: Weak fuzzy complex number, weak fuzzy complex vector space, weak fuzzy complex inner product.

Short Introduction

Fuzzy sets defined by Zadeh in [4], were used in many mathematical contexts, In [1], we find the concept of weak fuzzy complex numbers as a new generalization of real numbers. This class was used in defining weak fuzzy complex vector spaces [3] is a similar discussion with respect to neutrosophic vector spaces [2,5,6].

In this work, we study the inner products defined over weak fuzzy complex vector spaces, and we explain our ideas in terms of theorems and some related examples.

Main concepts

Definition:

Let $Cw = \{a + b\varepsilon; a, b \in R\}$ be the ring of weak fuzzy complex numbers with $t = \varepsilon \in]0,1[$.

Let V be a vector space over the real field R , we define the fuzzy weak complex vector space V_w as follows:

$$V_w = \{x + y\varepsilon ; x, y \in V\}.$$

We define addition on V_w as follows:

$$(x + y\varepsilon) + (z + t\varepsilon) = (x + z) + (y + t)\varepsilon$$

We define the multiplication as follows:

$$(a + b\varepsilon). (x + y\varepsilon) = ax + byt + \varepsilon(ay + bx) ; x, y \in V, a, b \in R.$$

Theorem.

$(V_w, +, \cdot)$ Is a module over the ring C

Definition.

Let $V_w = V + V\varepsilon$ be a weak fuzzy complex vector space over C_w , Consider $g: V \times V \rightarrow R$ a classical inner product on V . We define the corresponding weak fuzzy complex inner product as follows:

$$g_w: V_w \times V_w \rightarrow R \quad \text{such that} \quad g_w(x_1 + x_2\varepsilon, y_1 + y_2\varepsilon) = g(x_1, y_1) + g(x_2, y_2)t + \varepsilon[g(x_1, y_2) + g(x_2, y_1)].$$

Now, we will discuss some properties of (V_w, g_w) .

Property 1.

Let $x = x_1 + x_2\varepsilon \in V_w$, then:

$$g_w(x, x) = g(x_1, x_1) + g(x_2, x_2)t + \varepsilon[g(x_1, x_2) + g(x_2, x_1)] = \|x_1\|^2 + \|x_2\|^2t + 2g(x_1, x_2)\varepsilon.$$

Property 2.

If $g_w(x, x) = 0$, then:

$$\begin{cases} \|x_1\|^2 + \|x_2\|^2t = 0 \dots (1) \\ g(x_1, x_2) = 0 \dots (2) \end{cases}$$

For equation (2), we get that $x_1 \perp x_2$ in V .

On the other hand, we have from (1) the following:

$$0 \leq \|x_1\|^2 = -\|x_2\|^2t \leq 0$$

Which is possible if and only if $t = 0$ or $\|x_1\| = \|x_2\| = 0$.

If we assumed that $t \neq 0$, then $x_1 = x_2 = 0$ and $X = 0$.

Property 3.

$$g_w(X, Y) = g_w(Y, X) ; \forall X, Y \in V_w.$$

Property 4.

Let $X = x_1 + x_2\varepsilon, Y = y_1 + y_2\varepsilon, Z = z_1 + z_2\varepsilon \in V_w$, then $X + Y = (x_1 + y_1) + (x_2 + y_2)\varepsilon$.

$$g_w(X + Y, Z) = g(x_1 + y_1, z_1) + g(x_2 + y_2, z_2)t + \varepsilon[g(x_1 + y_1, z_2) + g(x_2 + y_2, z_1)].$$

On the other hand:

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_w(X, Z) + g_w(Y, Z) &= g(x_1, z_1) + g(x_2, z_2)t + g(y_1, z_1) + g(y_2, z_2)t \\
 &+ \varepsilon[g(x_1, z_2) + g(y_2, z_1) + g(y_2, z_2) + g(y_2, z_1)] \\
 &= g(x_1 + y_1, z_1) + g(x_2 + y_2, z_2)t + \varepsilon[g(x_1 + y_1, z_2) + g(x_2 + y_2, z_1)] \\
 &= g_w(X + Y, Z)
 \end{aligned}$$

Property 5.

Let $X = x_1 + x_2\varepsilon, Y = y_1 + y_2\varepsilon \in V_w, A = a_1 + a_2\varepsilon \in C_w$, then:

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_w(AX, Y) &= g_w(a_1x_1 + a_2x_2t + \varepsilon[a_1x_2 + a_2x_1], y_1 + y_2\varepsilon) \\
 &= g(a_1x_1 + a_2x_2t, y_1) + g(a_1x_2 + a_2x_1, y_2)t + g(y_1, z_1) + g(y_2, z_2)t \\
 &+ \varepsilon[g(a_1x_1 + a_2x_2t, y_2) + g(a_1x_2 + a_2x_1, y_1)] \\
 &= a_1g(x_1, y_1) + a_2tg(x_2, y_1) + a_1tg(x_2, y_2) + a_2tg(x_2, y_2) \\
 &+ \varepsilon[a_1g(x_1, y_2) + a_2tg(x_2, y_2) + a_1g(x_2, y_1) + a_2g(x_1, y_1)]
 \end{aligned}$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned}
 A.g_w(X, Y) &= (a_1 + a_2\varepsilon)[g(x_1, y_1) + g(x_2, y_2)t + \varepsilon[g(x_1, y_2) + g(x_2, y_1)]] \\
 &= a_1g(x_1, y_1) + a_2tg(x_2, y_1) + a_1tg(x_2, y_2) + a_2tg(x_2, y_2) \\
 &+ \varepsilon[a_1g(x_1, y_2) + a_2tg(x_2, y_2) + a_1g(x_2, y_1) + a_2g(x_1, y_1)]
 \end{aligned}$$

So that:

$$g_w(A.X, Y) = A.g_w(X, Y)$$

Property 6.

Take $X = x_1 + x_2\varepsilon, Y = y_1 + y_2\varepsilon \in V_w$, suppose that $X \perp Y$, then $g_w(X, Y) = 0$, hence:

$$g(x_1, y_1) + g(x_2, y_2)t + \varepsilon[g(x_1, y_2) + g(x_2, y_1)] = 0, \text{ thus:}$$

$$\begin{cases} g(x_1, y_1) + g(x_2, y_2)t = 0 \dots (1) \\ g(x_1, y_2) + g(x_2, y_1) = 0 \dots (2) \end{cases}$$

This implies that:

$$\begin{cases} g(x_1, y_1) = -g(x_2, y_2)t \dots (1) \\ g(x_1, y_2) = -g(x_2, y_1) \dots (2) \end{cases}$$

Definition.

Let W_w be a subspace of V_w , we define:

$$W_w^\perp = \{Y \in V_w; g_w(X, Y) = 0 \ \forall X \in W_w\}$$

Now, we will check if W_w^\perp is a subspace of V_w .

$\forall Y, Z \in W_w^\perp$, then for any $X \in W_w$, we have $g_w(X, Y) = g_w(X, Z) = 0$, thus $g_w(X, Y) - g_w(X, Z) = 0$, so that $g_w(X, Y - Z) = 0$, hence $Y - Z \in W_w^\perp$.

On the other hand, for any $A \in C_w$, we have:

$$g_w(A.Y, X) = A.g_w(Y, X) = A(0) = 0, \text{ thus } A.Y \in W_w^\perp \text{ is a subspace of } V_w.$$

Definition.

Let $X = x_1 + x_2\varepsilon \in V_w$, we define the conjugate vector as follows:

$$\bar{X} = x_1 - x_2\varepsilon$$

Remark.

$$g_w(X, \bar{X}) = g(x_1, x_1) - g(x_2, x_2)t + \varepsilon[g(x_1, x_2) + g(x_2, x_1)] = \|x_1\|^2 - \|x_2\|^2t$$

If $t \neq 0$, then $X \perp \bar{X}$ if and only if $t = \frac{\|x_1\|^2}{\|x_2\|^2}$.

Definition.

We define the norm of X as follows:

$$\|X\| = \sqrt{|f(X, \bar{X})|} = \sqrt{|\|x_1\|^2 - \|x_2\|^2t|}$$

Example.

Consider the Euclidean vector space $V = R^2$ over R .

Let V_w be the corresponding weak fuzzy complex vector space over C_w with $\varepsilon^2 = t = \frac{1}{2}$.

The ordinary inner product on V is defined as follows:

$$g: V \times V \rightarrow R; g[(x, y), (z, t)] = xz + yt$$

Let $X = (1,2) + (1,0)\varepsilon, Y = (1,1) + (2,1)\varepsilon$, then:

$$g_w(X, Y) = g[(1,2), (1,1)] + g[(1,0), (2,1)]t + \varepsilon[g[(1,2), (2,1)] + g[(1,0), (1,1)]] = 3 + (2)\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon[4 + 1] = 4 + 5\varepsilon.$$

Also, $\bar{X} = (1,2) - (1,0)\varepsilon = (1,2) + (-1,0)\varepsilon, \|X\| = \sqrt{|5 - \frac{1}{2}|} = \sqrt{\frac{9}{2}} = \frac{3}{\sqrt{2}}$

Remark.

Take $X = x_1 + x_2\varepsilon, Y = y_1 + y_2\varepsilon$, let us find the relation between $g_w(\bar{X}, Y)$ and $g_w(X, \bar{Y})$:

$$g_w(\bar{X}, Y) = g_w(x_1 - x_2\varepsilon, y_1 + y_2\varepsilon) = g(x_1, y_1) - g(x_2, y_2)t + \varepsilon[g(x_1, y_2) - g(x_2, y_1)]$$

$$g_w(X, \bar{Y}) = g_w(x_1 + x_2\varepsilon, y_1 - y_2\varepsilon) = g(x_1, y_1) - g(x_2, y_2)t + \varepsilon[g(x_1, -y_2) + g(x_2, y_1)]$$

$$= g(x_1, y_1) - g(x_2, y_2)t - \varepsilon[g(x_1, y_2) - g(x_2, y_1)]$$

This implies that $g_w(\bar{X}, Y) = \overline{g_w(X, \bar{Y})}$.

If $X \perp Y$, then according to property (6), we have:

$$\begin{cases} -g(x_2, y_2) = g(x_1, y_1) \\ -g(x_2, y_1) = g(x_1, y_2) \end{cases}$$

This implies that:

$$g_w(\bar{X}, Y) = 2g(x_1, y_1) + 2\varepsilon g(x_1, y_2).$$

Remark.

Take $X = x_1 + x_2\varepsilon, Y = y_1 + y_2\varepsilon$, then:

$$\|X + Y\|^2 = g_w(X + Y, \bar{X} + \bar{Y}) = g_w(X, \bar{X}) + g_w(X, \bar{Y}) + g_w(Y, \bar{X}) + g_w(Y, \bar{Y})$$

$$= \|X\|^2 + \|Y\|^2 + 2g(x_1, y_1) - 2g(x_2, y_2)t$$

If $X \perp Y$, then $-2g(x_2, y_2)t = 2g(x_1, y_1)$, thus:

$$\|X + Y\|^2 = \|X\|^2 + \|Y\|^2 + 4g(x_1, y_1)$$

Remark.

According to Cauchy-Schwartz inequality, we can write:

$$|g(x_1, y_1)| \leq \|x_1\| \cdot \|y_1\|$$

Thus, $\|X + Y\|^2 = \|x_1\|^2 + \|y_1\|^2 + 4\|x_1\| \cdot \|y_1\|$.

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